

D1.4 Dissemination and Communication Campaign

WP1 Project Management, Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication

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PROJECT DETAILS AND DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

PROJECT DETAILS

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

PROJECT DETAILS AND DELIVERABLE INFORMATION	2
GLOSSARY OF ACRONYMS.....	5
1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
2. COMMUNICATION MONITORING & CONTROL	7
3. COMMUNICATION ACTIONS	8
3.1 Twitter account.....	8
3.2 Instagram account.....	9
3.3 RESORB's website	10
3.4 RESORB's Gmail Account.....	11
3.5 ResearchGate project page	11
3.6 Communication with cancer patient associations.....	12
3.7 Participation to national/international conferences	17
3.8 Press and Web News Release	17
3.9 Participation to popular science events.....	18
3.10 Dissemination actions	18
3.11 Collaborations with industries	18
4. BIBLIOGRAPHY/REFERENCES	19

GLOSSARY OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Extended Definition
CD	Communication Descriptor
DCC	Dissemination and Communication Campaign
KVI	Key Value Indicator
UNIFI	Università di Pisa

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of the deliverable D1.4 Dissemination and Communication Campaign (DCC) is to detail, monitor, and refine the implementation of the RESORB's dissemination and communication plan [1]. In particular, the DCC identifies the tools we have exploited for sharing the RESORB vision and results with the targeted audiences. Moreover, this document identifies indicators of the effectiveness of our dissemination and communication campaigns. Such indicators will give us appropriate feedbacks to improve and/or adjust our communication actions.

The implementation of the dissemination and communication campaigns is fully integrated into RESORB through the WP1 led by UNIP. However, all the consortium members have been involved in the implementation and monitoring of the communication campaign. In this regard, the DCC can be considered as a living document, which we will be updated as soon as any action of the communication campaign is implemented and/or changed. All the RESORB partners will contribute to the updating of the DCC and will receive a copy of the amended DCC.

2. COMMUNICATION MONITORING & CONTROL

A key point of the RESORB communication plan and strategy is generating an optimal flow of information between the RESORB "universe" and possible stakeholders at any moment in time. In this regard, it is essential to monitor and control the RESORB communication and to assess the information both flow and impact with respect to the dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan [1]. To this end, we identified the following communication descriptors (CDs) and key value indicators (KVI):

Communication Descriptors:

- Author(s) and Contributor(s) of any action (source: RESORB partners)
- Type of the action (source: RESORB partners);
- Flow direction, namely, one-way exchange such as website and press release or two-way exchange such as exhibition, school visit (source: RESORB partners);
- Main recipients (source: RESORB partners and analytical tools)
- Date of the monitoring process (source: RESORB partners and analytical tools)
- Place of the action, such as webpage, conference site (source: RESORB partners)
- Content of the action (e.g., posts, press release, (source: RESORB partners)

Key value indicators (i.e., size and/or impact of the action):

- Number of visitors, downloads, documents, events on the RESORB project website (source: Google Search Console)
- Number of followers, followings, reads, likes, and posts on the social media (source: Twitter-, ResearchGate-, LinkedIn-own statistics)
- Number of stakeholders reached (source: RESORB partners),

- Number of external events with participation of the consortium partners (source: RESORB partners)
- Number of participants in RESORB-own events (source: participants list)

The outcomes of the monitoring process will be used to timely adjust the communication campaign and meet the goals of the communication plan, or to change and improve this latter. After making changes to the communication campaign, we will frequently monitor their effect through DCs and KVIs to determine the result of the modifications we made. This loop between 1) campaign, 2) monitor, and 3) control will allow reaching the largest number of target stakeholders, thus, extending the impact of RESORB beyond its lifecycle.

3. COMMUNICATION ACTIONS

To implement the communication plan we used various tools/channels with their own specificity, which depends on several aspects including the targeted audience (i.e., general vs. specialized) or the way to communicate (i.e., one-way exchange vs. two-way exchange).

3.1 Twitter account.

The Twitter account of RESORB, after it's birth in May 2022, has started collecting followers and informing a broad audience (e.g., oncologists, citizens, and research labs) about the project aims, status, and achievements.

The RESORB Twitter account has the following DCs and KVI:

Author(s)	Type	Exchange direction	Main recipient	Date	Place	Content	Size
UNIFI	Social media	One-way	1. Civic society 2. Research community	19/09/2022	https://twitter.com/resorb_project/	Posts	Followings = 13 Followers = 12 Tweets&Replies= 5

We expect to further improve the KVI of the project Twitter account in the following months when RESORB will lead to additional scientific results.

3.2 Instagram account.

A RESORB's Instagram account has been created on September 30th to inform the general public, but also scientific community and industrial professionals, about the project aims, status, and achievements.

The RESORB Instagram account has the following DCs and KVI:

Author(s)	Type	Exchange direction	Main recipient	Date	Place	Content	Size
UNIFI	Social media	One-way	1. Civic society 2. Research community	19/09/2022	https://twitter.com/resorb_project/	Posts	Followings = 2 Followers = 2 Posts= 2

Data about the audience reached by the Instagram account will be updated in future release of this document.

3.3 RESORB's website

The website of the project, lunched on May 27th 2022, has informed the civic society about the RESORB vision and impacts through the content of the Home, Project, and News&Events pages, as well as specialized audience by posting job opportunities, new entries and recent publications in the Publications and Partners pages.

The main DCs and KVIs of the project website are:

Author(s)	Type	Exchange direction	Main recipient	Date	Place	Content	Size
RESORB partners	Web content	One-way	1. Civic society 2. Research community	19/09/2022	https://www.resorb-project.eu	RESORB at glance, Consortium composition, News & Events, Publications,	Unknown*

*The size of the audience we reached through the website is still unknown. However, being aware of the key role that both size and composition of the website visitors have on our communication plan, we set an analytical tool (i.e. Google Search Console) to gather these data. A screenshot of Google Search Console indexing the project website is shown here below.

We will update the DCC including the audience reached with the project website in the following months.

3.4 RESORB's Gmail Account

RESORB has a Gmail account (i.e., resorbproject@gmail.com) that we will allow communicating directly with RESORB's subscribers and inform them about the status of the project, its outcomes, and related events.

3.5 ResearchGate project page

The ResearchGate page of RESORB has been used to inform the scientific community about the project aims, status, and achievements.

The screenshot shows the ResearchGate project page for 'RESORB: On-Demand Bioresorbable OptoElectronic System for In-Vivo and In-Situ Monitoring of Chemotherapeutic Drugs' by Giuseppe Barillaro. The page includes a search bar, navigation links (Home, Questions, Jobs), and a sidebar with statistics: Updates (0 new, 1), Recommendations (0 new, 1), Followers (0 new, 6), and Reads (16 new, 38). The project description states it is an EIC Pathfinder Open project funded by the EC, aiming to develop bioresorbable chemical sensing systems. The date is 1 April 2022 - 31 March 2025, and the lab is Giuseppe Barillaro's Lab. A 'Share' button and a dropdown menu are visible at the bottom right.

The RESORB Research Gate page has the following DCs and KVIs:

Author(s)	Type	Exchange direction	Main recipient	Date	Place	Content	Size
UNIPI on the behalf of the CA	Web content	One-way	1. Research community	20/09/2022	Link to the page*	RESORB at glance, News & Events, Publications,	Updates = 1 Recommendations = 1 Followers = 6 Reads = 38
* https://www.researchgate.net/project/RESORB-On-Demand-Bioresorbable-OptoElectronic-System-for-In-Vivo-and-In-Situ-Monitoring-of-Chemotherapeutic-Drugs?amp%3B_esc=lab_detail							

3.6 Communication with cancer patient associations

In order to raise awareness about the RESORB technology and assess acceptance in view of possible technology transfer from lab to market, we plan to prepare a number of anonymous questionnaires specifically tailored to target groups we want to reach. At first, we decided to target cancer patient associations (e.g., European Cancer Patient Coalition – ECPS [2]) and prepared a questionnaire aimed at measuring the level of acceptance of our technology by patients that are or have been under chemotherapy. The questionnaire is below reported.

Anonymous Questionnaire

Patient description		
1. What is your sex?		
	Male	
	Female	
	Intersex	
	Prefer not answer	
2. What is your age?		
	0-15 years old	
	15-30 years old	
	30-45 years old	
	45+	
	Prefer not answer	
3. Which of the following best describes your current professional occupation?		
Management		Sales
Healthcare practitioners		Healthcare support
Education, training, and library		Computer and mathematics
Food preparation		Farming, fishing, and forestry
Construction and extraction		Installation, maintenance, and repair
Community and social service		Personal care and service
Architecture and engineering		Business and finance
Office and administrative support		Arts, design, entertainment, sports, media
Building and grounds cleaning and maintenance		Legal occupations
Life, physical, and social science		Production occupations
Protective service occupations		Transportation and materials moving
Other (please specify)		
4. Are you currently taking chemotherapeutic drugs?		
	Yes	
	No	
	Prefer not answer	
(If you answered yes to the previous question) How long have you been taking chemotherapeutic drugs?		

	0-2 months	
	2-4 months	
	4-6 months	
	Prefer not answer	

Patient awareness about implantable and bioresorbable technologies			
1. Are you aware of the existence of implantable biomedical devices?			
	YES	I DON'T KNOW	NO
2. Do you have any biomedical implants in your body (e.g., a pacemaker)?			
		YES	NO
	(If you answered YES) which kind of implants?		
3. Do you know people that have received a biomedical implant in their body?			
		YES	NO
4. Are you familiar with the concept of biocompatibility?			
	YES	I DON'T KNOW	NO
5. Are you familiar with the concept of bioresorbability?			
	YES	I DON'T KNOW	NO
6. Do you know that certain materials dissolve in the human body in safe products?			
		YES	NO
7. Do you know that the human body can safely dissolve an implant if suitable materials are used?			

	YES	NO
8. Are you familiar with the concepts of nanotechnology or nanomaterials?		
	YES	I DON'T KNOW
		NO

Patient willingness to use the RESORB technology, once available					
Concerning the possibility to receive a fully bioresorbable and implantable device to monitor chemotherapeutic drugs in future.					
1. I would like to have it					
STRONGLY AGREE	MODERATELY AGREE	MILDLY AGREE	MILDLY DISAGREE	MODERATELY DISAGREE	STRONGLY AGREE
2. I will feel comfortable in having it, both emotionally and physically					
STRONGLY AGREE	MODERATELY AGREE	MILDLY AGREE	MILDLY DISAGREE	MODERATELY DISAGREE	STRONGLY AGREE
3. I will feel confident in receiving it					
STRONGLY AGREE	MODERATELY AGREE	MILDLY AGREE	MILDLY DISAGREE	MODERATELY DISAGREE	STRONGLY AGREE
4. I will feel safe in receiving it					
STRONGLY AGREE	MODERATELY AGREE	MILDLY AGREE	MILDLY DISAGREE	MODERATELY DISAGREE	STRONGLY AGREE
5. It will help me to improve my health status					
STRONGLY AGREE	MODERATELY AGREE	MILDLY AGREE	MILDLY DISAGREE	MODERATELY DISAGREE	STRONGLY AGREE
6. It will help my physicians to better monitor my health status?					
STRONGLY	MODERATELY	MILDLY	MILDLY	MODERATELY	STRONGLY

AGREE	AGREE	AGREE	DISAGREE	DISAGREE	AGREE
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Assessment of possible patient prejudices			
1) Do you think that a fully bioresorbable and implantable sensor for monitoring in real-time the levels of a chemotherapeutic drug in the body might be advantageous for patients?			
	YES VERY MUCH	INDIFFERENT	NOT AT ALL
2) Do you think that a fully bioresorbable and implantable sensor for monitoring in real-time the level of chemotherapeutic drugs in your body might make you feel better controlled than using traditional blood tests?			
	YES VERY MUCH	INDIFFERENT	NOT AT ALL
3) Would be worried about receiving a bioresorbable implant?			
	YES VERY MUCH	INDIFFERENT	NOT AT ALL
4) Do you think that such an implant would have some family, social, and economic consequences in your life?			
	YES VERY MUCH	INDIFFERENT	NOT AT ALL
5) Do you think that chemotherapeutic drugs might have fewer side effects if the dosage is adjusted on the basis of the results coming from traditional blood test instead of a bioresorbable implant?			
	YES VERY MUCH	INDIFFERENT	NOT AT ALL
6) Do you think that the bioresorbable implant would improve your life with respect to frequent hospital accesses?			
	YES VERY MUCH	INDIFFERENT	NOT AT ALL

Please use this box for any comments or suggestions you wish to leave

3.7 Participation to national/international conferences

National Conferences

E. Mazzotta, T. Di Giulio, M. Corsi, S. Mariani, C. Malitesta, G. Barillaro, "A novel integration of molecularly imprinted polymers with nanoporous silicon for selective and sensitive optical detection of proteins". XXIX Congresso della Divisione di Chimica Analitica della Società Chimica Italiana, 11-15 September 2022, Messina (Italy)

International Conferences

Corsi, M., Paghi, A., Mariani, S., Golinelli, G., Debrassi, A., Egri, G., Leo, G., Vandini, E., Vilella, A., Dähne, L., Giuliani, D., Barillaro, G., "Implantable and Bioresorbable Nanostructured Fluorescence Sensor for In Vivo Ph Monitoring", 2022 IEEE SENSORS, 30th October-2nd November 2022, Dallas (US).

3.8 Press and Web News Release

RESORB "stories" are available at the UNIPi's news pages (UnipiNews) and web release:

<https://www.unipi.it/index.php/component/k2/item/23833-un-sensore-biorassorbibile-sottopelle-puo-monitorare-i-segnali-del-corpo?Itemid=637>; 23rd June 2022: "Un sensore biorassorbibile sottopelle può monitorare i segnali del corpo" (English translation: A bioresorbable sensor implanted under the skin to monitor body signals);

<https://www.unipi.it/index.php/component/k2/item/22464-finanziato-resorb-il-primo-progetto-del-nuovo-programma-europeo-horizon-europe?Itemid=637>; 19th November 2021: "Finanziato RESORB, il primo progetto del nuovo programma europeo Horizon Europe" (English translation: the new European Horizon Europe program has funded RESORB);

https://www.repubblica.it/salute/2022/08/03/news/sensore_sottopelle_effetto_farmac_i-360056468/; 3rd August 2022: "E con un sensore sottopelle sapremo se i farmaci fanno effetto" (English translation: A sensor under the skin will finally tell us whenever drugs are effective);

<https://medicoepaziente.it/2022/biosensori-impiantabili-la-nuova-frontiera-della-diagnostica/>; 6th August 2022; "Biosensori impiantabili. La nuova frontiera della

diagnostica” (English translation: Implantable biosensors: the new frontier in diagnostics).

3.9 Participation to popular science events

In order to raise awareness of the RESORB technology and gain social acceptance, we participated and/or planned to participate to the following popular science events:

Bright Night, the EU Research Nigh 2022.

Author(s)	Title	Location Date	Audience Size
G. Barillaro (UNIFI)	Nanosensori biodegradabili: come potrebbe cambiare il monitoraggio di cibo, ambiente e salute (oral presentation) (English translation: Biodegradable nanosensors: how they would impact the monitoring of food, environment and health)	Pisa 30.09.2022	*
E. Mazzotta (UNISAL)	Biomimetic receptors in bioresorbable sensors (poster presentation)	Lecce 30.09.2022	*
* to be updated on 30 th September 2022			

3.10 Dissemination actions

RESORB has a new gold open-access publication:

Corsi, M., Paghi, A., Mariani, S., Golinelli, G., Debrassi, A., Egri, G., Leo, G., Vandini, E., Vilella, A., Dähne, L., Giuliani, D., Barillaro, “*Bioresorbable Nanostructured Chemical Sensor for Monitoring of pH Level In Vivo*”, *Adv. Sci.* 2022, 2202062 (DOI: 10.1002/advs.202202062); <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/advs.202202062>

3.11 Collaborations with industries

The RESORB technology has attracted the attention of “ab medica” a company that operates in the biomedical sector by offering appropriate, inclusive, sustainable patient care through the integration of clinical pathways with the best techniques and technologies available. Precisely, UNIFI and ab medica are discussing possible collaborations for the development of a wireless device that will read data recorded by the RESORB optical

sensors once implanted in the body and make them available to patient and doctors through a mobile app.

4. BIBLIOGRAPHY/REFERENCES

1. RESORB Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan
2. <http://www.ecpc.org>